

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF W-SHAPED DEPLOYABLE COMPOSITE BOOM

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Abstract

Thin-walled composite booms have been widely applied in micro-satellites due to their simple structure form. This paper presents a new design with an open structure for secondary load-bearing booms. The geometry of the boom and ply stack sequence were optimized to reduce stress concentrations. The design boundary of the ply stacking sequence was proposed. The damage of the structure was analysed in finite element method. Samples manufactured in advanced pultrusion process (ADP) had good performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to the requirements of small-sized and multi-functional satellites, supporting structures of antennas and solar cells are designed as deployable booms. Currently, the support structures are fabricated by thin-ply composite, where the bending stiffness and the winding stress should be considered [1]. Researchers of Sapienza analysed the utility of 1m long boom with conforming material and experimental platform for the smallsat [2]. Ömer Soykasap prepared a boom with T300 carbon/polyetherimide with a folding hinge for deployment [3]. Zhongyi Chu had developed a design theory for a deployable boom [4]. Bai studied the folding behaviour of the thin-walled booms manufactured by vacuum bags, and experimental results were in good agreement with the finite element model [5].

This work presents a new deployable composite boom with a simple shape, good reliability and high tolerance of manufacturing defects. Finite element analysis (FEA) method was adopted to study the influences of geometric parameters, ply angles and sequences on the bending behavior of the composite boom proposed in this paper. Numerical results verified by experiments show that the stiffness of the W-shaped composite boom is larger than the common-used C-shaped composite boom. Moreover, the FEM can be used to predict the failure of the composite boom.

2 DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF W-SHAPED BOOM

In order to accomplish future space exploration, light structures are proposed with high deployment reliability, controlled deployment behavior and predictable deployed dynamics [6]. In view of the different needs of small satellites, there are currently two main cross-sections of composite deployable booms, closed cross-sections and open cross-sections. As the main bearing structure, the former one was endowed with high bending rigidity but hard to rewind. In the support structure of the spacecraft, the closing boom is usually applied in the main support boom, and the opening structure is used as the secondary support boom. In this paper, a secondary support boom with an open cross-section is proposed, which length is 4m with a section line length of 70 mm and a thickness of 0.2 mm.

In its working condition, the boom will be rolled on a cylinder of 80mm diameter in satellite and then deployed in space. To achieve a good supporting performance, composite boom should be rolled without defects. Thus, deformation mechanism of boom should be well studied. To solve above problems, a new form of the composite boom is designed with a W-shaped cross-section, as shown in Fig. 1. Influencing parameters of this structure's bending stiffness are studied for desirable mechanical performance. Design parameters would be optimized to achieve desired results, including geometric shape, ply stacking sequence.

2.1 Geometric Parameters

The cross-sectional shape of the deployable boom is designed as W shape. Thus, a larger bending stiffness of boom can be obtained with increasing height and same cross section length. To investigate the relationship between geometric parameters and bending stiffness of W-shaped boom, a FEA model was developed and three parameters were involved in. Geometric parameters are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 : Geometric variables of the boom.

A FEA model was established to optimise the whole boom structure with Abaqus/Standard solver. In this model, a one-meter-long boom was built by the shell element, which the type of element is s4r. The stacking sequence was [0/90/0], which is a common orthogonal stacking sequence. The boom was flattened by two rollers which diameter was 800 mm, in the first step. And in the following step, the deformed boom was imported into the new model as the initial state, and one of the boom's end fixed on a roller by tie connection. And another end was given a backward pull force. Then the angle of rotation was given to the roller when the boom was being rolled up. To reduce the calculation time, the experiment only performed step1. To study the influence of geometric parameters on the deformation of composite boom, four shapes of composite involved in the finite element calculation process, which are shown in Table 1. In Figure 2, the nephogram shows that there are stress concentration zones at the dome of the inner and outer arcs, where the value of stress is from 260mpa to 322map regarding different types. What can be found in the stress nephogram is that the stress concentration would be reduced with the decreasing H value and ratio of inner radius to outer radius. And the degree of stress concentration is related to the radius of the arc. To reduce the stress concentration, the R1 and R2 should be as close as possible with a limited length.

Type	R1 (mm)	R2 (mm)	H (mm)
a	4	9	2
b	5	8	4.5
c	5	9	1.4
d	6	8	4

Table 1 The parameters of different w-shape booms' structure.

Figure 2 The stress distribution of different type of boom.

Results show that when the radius of inner arc is close to that of outer arc, desirable stiffness can be obtained without excessive stress. According to stress distribution with different geometric parameters, type 4 is chosen as the final configuration of composite boom.

2.2 Ply Stacking Sequence

Once the cross-section is determined, the ply stacking sequence is the key factor of bending stiffness. Mechanical properties of the boom with different layup sequences are studied in this section.

The thickness of the whole rod is less than 0.2 mm, and the thickness of the prepreg is 0.03mm, so the number of layers of the boom is 6 or 7. Several discrete parameters of the sample were made.

As shown in Fig.3, some fibre fractures are generated during the rolling process when the stack sequence is $[45/90/-45]$ s. Thus, the surface layer should be 0-angled ply to avoid the fibre fractures of outermost ply during the rolling process.

According to further investigation, it can be found that the stiffness of laminate is too large to roll, if the layers of laminates are larger than 7, as shown in Fig. 4.

Therefore, in following FEA process, the layers of this structure is 6 and layers of upper and lower surface are 0 angled layer.

Figure 3 The surface fracture of the boom.

Figure 4 Fracture of the 7-layer specimen.

To study the deflection behaviour of boom and its resistance to pressure deformation, several configurations are involved in finite element analysis, which can be seen in Table 2. In detail, deflection of boom depends on the 0-layers. And pressure resistance is related to 90-layers.

NO.	Layer sequence
a	$[0/45/-45]_s$
b	$[0/90/90]_s$
c	$[0/90/0]_s$
d	$[0/0/90]_s$

Table 2 Different stacking sequence of the FEA model.

A finite element model was built to test the mechanical properties of different ply stacking sequence. The W-shape boom was placed on the analytical rigid body plate and is flattened to a height of 1.5 mm by a $\phi 80$ mm cylindrical body. The results are shown in Fig. 5. The bar chart of resistance to pressure deformation shows the ability of the w-shaped bar to resist pressure, which reflects the dimensional stability of the boom. Meanwhile, another one shows the deflection level of the boom, which reflects the load carrying capacity of the boom. It is found that structure fracture trend to happen when the surface ply of boom is not a zero-angle ply. The horizontal ply will be beneficial to the accuracy of the cross-sectional shape and effective increasing of the moment of inertia. The plies in the zero-angle ply can reduce the deflection. It can be seen in Fig. 5 that a boom with a stacking sequence of type C can obtain a good overall performance.

Figure 5 Influence of different types of ply stacking sequences on resistance to pressure deformation and deflection.

2.3 Fabrication of W-Shape Boom with Advance Pultrusion Process

Advanced pultrusion is an ideal manufacturing method for specific cross section shaped composite with large length. In this paper, a w-shaped composite boom in 4m length was manufactured based on the advanced pultrusion process (ADP), as shown in Fig. 6.

The equipment of ADP involved in this paper is shown in Fig. 7. This equipment consists of three units, a traction unit, a curing unit, and a discharge unit. The traction unit comprises two sets of traction chucks that can alternately draw the booms forward and apply tractive force to the boom along with the discharge unit. The curing unit consists of three parts: precuring part, curing part and post-curing part. The prepreg stack in flat form will be changed into the W shape in the precuring part. Then the prepreg will be cured in the curing parts over 90% curing degree. Finally, the boom will be cured completely in the post-curing part.

To achieve above process, the temperature 120°C, 180°C and 200°C respectively in precuring, curing and post-curing parts. The pulling speed of the traction unit is 10mm/min. After curing unit, the curing degree of the boom can reach 98%.

Figure 6 Manufacturing process and actual w-shaped composite boom.

Figure 7 The advanced pultrusion equipment

3 FAILURE MODEL

Based on its structural characters, a two-dimensional Hashin failure criterion was used to investigate the in-plane damage of the w-shaped boom during its rolling process.

The failure modes included in Hashin's criteria are as follows[7].

Tensile fibre failure for $\sigma_{11} \geq 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Compressive fibre failure for $\sigma_{11} < 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Tensile matrix failure for $\sigma_{22} > 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Compressive matrix failure for $\sigma_{22} < 0$

$$\left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 - 1\right]\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_C}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

A rolling model was established to analyse the rolling behaviour of boom with Hashin's failure criteria. The result is shown in the Fig. 8. The top of the arc will be pressured during the flattening process, leading to a transverse compress within the boom, so it is a region with a high risk of failure.

Figure 8 Hashin's matrix compressive damage during rolling process

4 CONCLUSIONS

The w-shaped composite boom can achieve a better deploy ability and a simpler manufacturing process, compared with closed structure composite booms. Uniform distribution of overall stress of W-shaped boom will be achieved with two close adjacent arcs. The surface ply is more efficient, so the stacking sequence design needs to be optimised to meet the different demand. When the boom is rolled and flattened, fractures trends to happen on the top of the arc. The advanced pultrusion process can be used to manufacture booms in the required length.

The critical height of the thin-walled boom can be determined by the rolling radius and the mechanical properties of the material. A further study will be done on the straightness of boom manufactured by ADP.

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